

1998

2007

**10 YEAR
ANNIVERSARY SPECIAL**

EUROPEAN UNION ROAD FEDERATION (ERF)

INTERNATIONAL ROAD FEDERATION (IRF)
Brussels Programme Centre

Foreword by the President

Dear friends and colleagues,

Ten years have gone by since a group of forward-looking individuals decided that roads ought to have a strong representation in the city where the political future of the European continent is decided on a day-to-day basis: Brussels.

After some discussions, the European Union Road Federation (ERF) was born in 1998 under the auspices of promoting a fair debate on the role of road infrastructure in Europe. The Federation, OUR Federation, immediately became a key stakeholder for all discussions and policy-making decision over the role of roads and their place in society. A role which would grow over time, thanks to the tremendous efforts of the Federation's Secretariat and the drive of its ever increasing Membership.

Since January 2006, increased strength has been bestowed on its operations as the ERF became the Brussels Programme Centre of the International Road Federation (IRF), thus expanding the scope of its activities, the membership serviced and the available pool of resources.

The coming years will certainly offer new challenges to our Federation on a wide variety of topics, since the ERF – IRF BPC has led and continues to lead important battles in the advancement of better roads both in Europe and beyond. I am confident that the ERF – IRF BPC will be able, as it has done in the past, to deliver the appropriate answers on behalf of the entire road infrastructure sector, either on its own or in synergy with the other Brussels-based transport associations.

Many years as President of this Federation have confirmed to me that our project has three assets of paramount importance and without which it could not perform to the current standard: its Members, its staff and a clear set of principles and values which enlightens its action. It is these three important factors, in fact, which ultimately determine the enormous success that our project enjoys: yesterday, today and tomorrow.

With my best regards,

Aniceto Zaragoza

President and Chairman of the Executive Committee

European Union Road Federation (ERF),
the Brussels Programme Centre of the International Road Federation (IRF)

Foreword by the Secretary General

Dear friends and colleagues,

In this special publication we look back on 10 years of our Federation's presence at the heart of Europe's capital. The decision to open a representative office in September 1998 was made under the correct assumption that the European Union would take on a decisive importance in transport matters at the international scale.

Time has proved that the road sector simply could not afford to be absent from Brussels.

From the recognition of the socio-economic importance of roads and the contribution of infrastructure to road safety, to the building-up of a wealth of services that would animate a true European road community, our task has not always been easy. However, a passionate team and a committed membership have taken the Federation where it is today: a well-established platform that condenses the road sector's input on mobility issues, runs a dialogue with all relevant stakeholders, initiates research and promotes a better knowledge of our sector, both at the European and the international level.

I still remember the early meetings of Richard Diment, Wolfgang Neumann, Christian Gerondeau, Lars-Gunnar Tannerfors and Aniceto Zaragoza back in 1997, those visionaries that against all odds were resolved to build up a new project and counted on a young, unexperienced professional like me to do so. I hope the five of them feel proud about what has been achieved.

We have chosen to illustrate these ten years of our action through the description of activities that I believe have marked our sector. Some have been outright successes, others have illustrated the need for a more pedagogic approach, all have proved the importance of constant vigilance and the need to be loyal to our Federation's core mission.

As our office faces fresh challenges in its role as voice of the European and international road, let me finish by thanking each of you for ten years of excellent work together.

The adventure has just started, as the road is ahead of us. Let us make the trip enjoyable.

Yours,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "José Papi".

José Papi

Secretary General

European Union Road Federation (ERF),
the Brussels Programme Centre of the International Road Federation (IRF)

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1. Introduction

The European Union Road Federation (ERF), the Brussels Programme Centre of the International Road Federation (IRF) is a non-profit association which coordinates the views of Europe's road sector and acts as a platform for dialogue and research on mobility issues. As the **"Voice of the European Road"**, the ERF – IRF BPC promotes knowledge of the road sector through research, information services, and a permanent dialogue with all stakeholders. The Federation is run by a Plenary Assembly gathering all Members and by an Executive Committee gathering representatives elected by the Plenary Assembly. The ERF – IRF BPC is assisted by a Secretariat based in Brussels and headed by the Federation's Secretary General.

Born in 1998 as the European Union Road Federation (ERF), it quickly established itself at the heart of the road infrastructure debate within the EU thanks to its factual based approach to all road transport-related topics. The ERF became the association to talk to on all matters regarding road transport infrastructure and started to move beyond the areas of advocacy and communication and into European Commission co-funded research projects.

With its membership levels steadily increasing, the ERF constituted working groups to better involve Members in the topics of their interest and to aid in disseminating the knowledge gathered about EU policy. The ERF also reinforced its position as a credible research organisation when it submitted proposals and was awarded grants under the 6th Framework Programme of the European Union (2002 – 2006). In 2004 the 1st European Road Congress was organised in Lisbon to bring together road transport stakeholders to discuss the role of roads in the future of the European continent.

2006 was a year of considerable changes for the ERF when, following an agreement with the other Programme Centres, it became the Brussels Programme Centre of the International Road Federation (IRF). Along with a change in denomination (the Federation would, from now on, be referred to as ERF – IRF BPC) came an expansion of its global Membership to over 350 in more than 90 countries, as well as the possibility to work in synergy with the remaining two Programme Centre's of the IRF: Geneva and Washington. The ERF – IRF BPC then elected Members from its own Executive Committee to the IRF's World Executive Board to define its global strategy.

In November of the same year the 2nd European Road Congress was held in Brussels, drawing a large number of participants to debate and discuss the future of European road transport policy. One of the immediate steps that followed the key recommendations which emerged from the Congress was the creation, in 2007, of the IRF Research Council, a horizontal catalyst of expertise and skills committed to improving the sustainability and efficiency of the road sector.

The ERF – IRF BPC is now preparing to tackle efficiently the problems posed by advocating the need for cleaner, safer, better financed and better maintained roads in Europe and will look back to its past experiences to learn from the valuable lessons gained from ten years in the Brussels "Arena".

I. Timeline of the European Union Road Federation and selected European events

1997	- Preparatory work undertaken to launch the European Union Road Federation (ERF)
1998	- 11 May, ERF formally launched at a meeting at the European Parliament between the five founding Members: the National Road Associations (NRAs) of Germany, Sweden, the UK, France and Spain. - Establishment of Working Groups on "Road Maintenance" and "TEN Bottlenecks and Missing Links" - Publication of ERF "Manifesto for roads" - Launch of "ERF Briefing" and "ERF Info-Packages" newsletters
1999	- Prodi Commission – Loyola de Palacio Commissioner in charge of Transport - Establishment of a Working Group on "Engineering Low Cost Measures" - Recommendations of the Working Group on "TEN Bottlenecks and Missing Links" delivered to the European Commission - Launch of ERF website
2000	- European Conference on Sustainable Investment in Road Maintenance, organised by the ERF - 1 st Edition of "Policy & Action" Newsletter
2001	- White Paper, European transport policy for 2010: time to decide - 1 st Edition of Socio-economic benefits of Roads to society
2002	- 1 st edition of European Road Statistics - Launch of the ERF "Road Safety Programme" - Launch of the "European Road Users' Charter"
2003	- 3 rd European Road Safety Action Programme released by European Commission - Launch of "Environment Programme" - Launch of "Infrastructure Financing Programme" - Launch of "Voice of the European Road" Newsletter
2004	- Barroso Commission – Jacques Barrot Commissioner in charge of Transport - ERF founding signatory of the European Road Safety Charter in Dublin - Launch of "Engineering Safer Roads" Newsletter - 1 st European Road Congress (Lisbon)
2005	- ERF moves offices to 113 Avenue Louise, Brussels - GIROADS project kick off - Launch of the ERF "Infrastructure Safety Forum"
2006	- European Commission proposal for a Directive on Road Infrastructure Safety Management - Launch of "Intelligent Roads" Newsletter - The ERF becomes the Brussels Programme Centre of the International Road Federation (IRF) - 2 nd European Road Congress (Brussels) - Agreement with the TAIEX Unit of the EC's DG Enlargement to run training workshops in Central & Eastern Europe
2007	- IRF Research Council created

2. Membership

Membership of the ERF – IRF BPC has steadily increased over the years, mirroring the increase in influence of the Federation and its emergence as a point of reference for the European road transport sector. Members of the ERF – IRF BPC benefit from a wide range of services which includes:

- Statutory rights
- Regular information service
- Strategic consultation over areas of interest
- Networking opportunities at Member-only events
- Free/discounted access to all publications and public events
- Participation in Working Groups
- Operational consultation over areas of interest

Membership is open to national road associations, industry associations and individual organisations and represents the backbone of the Federation, conferring it credibility, legitimacy and authority in the world stage.

I. Effective Members & Associate Members

Effective Membership is granted by the ERF – IRF BPC to the national road associations who have joined the Federation, whilst any other individual organisation or undertaking not falling under this definition is given the status of Associate Member. Furthermore, since the ERF became the Brussels Programme Centre of the International Road Federation (IRF), a new category of Membership has been created to include in the ERF – IRF BPC activities Members of other IRF Programme Centres. The European Union Road Federation, the Brussels Programme Centre of the International Road Federation (IRF) has, at the time of publication (10 October 2007), 44 Members, divided as follows:

Effective Members:

- Asociación Española de la Carretera (Spain)
- Centro Rodoviário Português (Portugal)
- Dansk Vejforening (Denmark)
- Opplysningsrådet for Veitrafikken – Norsk Veiforening (Norway)
- Road Federation Belgium (Belgium)
- Road Users Alliance (UK)
- Suomen Tieyhdistys (Finland)

Associate Members:

- 3M Europe, S.A. (Belgium)
- Abertis Infraestructuras (Spain)
- ArcelorMittal (Luxembourg/India)
- Asebal (Spain)
- Ayuda Del Automovilista - ADA (Spain)
- Centro de Investigación y Desarrollo en Automoción - CIDAUT (Spain)
- Confederation of Organisations in Road Transport Enforcement - CORTE (Belgium)
- Delta Bloc GmbH (Austria)

- Efkon AG (Austria)
- Elsamex (Spain)
- Galva Union (France)
- Grupo GMV (Spain)
- Hierros y Aplanaciones S.A. - HIASA (Spain)
- Highway Industries Confederation Ltd. (UK)
- Hill & Smith Ltd. (UK)
- Les Bois de Tertu (France)
- L.I.E.R - Laboratoire d'essais INRETS des Equipements de la Route
- Marcegaglia (Italy)
- Metalmeccanica Fracasso S.P.A. (Italy)
- Outimex AG (Germany)
- Prismo Limited (United Kingdom)
- Safe German Guardrail Technology - SGGT (Germany)
- The Spanish Association of Manufacturers of Steel Road Restraint Systems - SIMEPROVI (Spain)
- SCT Italia (Italy)
- Snoline S.P.A. (Italy)
- Sociedad Ibérica de Construcciones Eléctricas S.A. - SICE (Spain)
- Solosar (France)
- SOMARO (France)
- SOVITEC - Beads Belgium Sprl (Belgium)
- Studiengesellschaft für Stahlschutzplanken e.V. (Germany)
- SWARCO Holding GmbH (Austria)
- Telefon Gradnja (Croatia)
- TUBOSIDER S.P.A. (Italy)
- Unipromet d.o.o. (Serbia-Montenegro)
- Voestalpine GmbH (Austria)
- Volkmann & Rossbach (Germany)
- WIMED Zakład Produkcji Znaków Drogowych (Poland)

II. Gold Members

In addition to ordinary Membership, Gold Membership was started in 2005 to particularly reward those organisations which leant outstanding support to all the activities of the ERF – IRF BPC. Current Gold Members are:

Asociación Española de la Carretera

For over fifty years, Assciación Española de la Carretera (AEC) has dedicated an intense effort to the promotion of more and better highways. AEC targets its research activities at road safety, environmental aspects and technical aspects of the road network.

Centro Rodoviário Português

The Portuguese Road Centre is an independent association which brings together the know-how and experience of all components of the road sector in Portugal.

3M Europe

Since inventing reflective materials over 60 years ago, 3M Traffic Safety Systems has been the worldwide leader in developing products, systems and services that help improve traffic safety and management.

ArcelorMittal

ArcelorMittal is the world's number one steel company, with 320,000 employees in more than 60 countries. The company brings together the world's number one and number two steel companies, Arcelor and Mittal Steel.

Abertis Infraestructuras

Abertis is Spain's leading private transport and communications infrastructure management corporation. It operates in the motorway industry, telecommunications infrastructure, airports, car parking and the development of logistics platforms.

III. Honorary Members

Honorary Members are individuals who, through their continued actions, have significantly contributed to the development of road transport and who are an inspiration to the entire road transport community.

The current Honorary Members are:

Aniceto Zaragoza Ramírez,

who served as Chairman of the ERF – IRF BPC from from 1998 to the present day and as Director General of the Spanish Road Association from 1992 to 2007. Dr. Zaragoza, one of the inspired figures of the European road transport sector, oversaw the birth of the Federation and the strengthening of its position as a point of reference in the road transport sector in Europe;

Christophe Nicodème,

an accomplished manager at Prismo Limited and a Member of the ERF – IRF BPC Executive Committee, Mr Nicodème offered, throughout the years, an invaluable contribution on why better roads make sense.

Marc Roegies,

who spent nearly four decades working for the Belgian road sector, both as a manager in the construction industry and as an administrator of several professional road associations;

Ola Bjornstad,

who has had extensive experience in the transport sector with the Norwegian Truck Owners Association, the Norwegian Transport Ministry and during his 13 year tenure as Director of the Norwegian Road Federation;

3. Statutory Meetings

Statutory Meetings have been held at least once per year from 1998 to the present day. Members gather in a Plenary Assembly to discuss and debate over the performance of the Federation and define the objectives for the immediate future. The Executive Committee, which is the elected body overseeing the activities of the ERF – IRF BPC throughout the year, also usually profits from the Statutory Meetings to hold one of its meetings.

Plenary Assemblies:

1998 – Brussels (launch Assembly), Brussels (Belgium)
 1999 – Lahti (Finland)
 2000 – Ravenna (Italy)
 2001 – Brussels (Belgium) (twice)
 2002 – Brussels (Belgium)
 2003 – Brussels (Belgium)
 2004 – Moscow (Russia)

2004 Plenary Assembly, Moscow

2005 – Brussels (Belgium)
 2006 – Alicante (Spain)
 2007 – Budapest (Hungary), Brussels (Belgium)

Executive Committee meetings:

1998 – Brussels (Belgium) (twice)
 1999 – Brussels (Belgium), Warsaw (Poland)
 2000 – Brussels (Belgium) (twice)
 2001 – Brussels (Belgium) (twice)
 2002 – Brussels (Belgium) (twice)
 2003 – Brussels (Belgium) (twice)
 2004 – Moscow (Russia)
 2005 – Brussels (Belgium) (three times)
 2006 – Alicante (Spain)
 2007 – Madrid (Spain), Budapest (Hungary), Brussels (Belgium)

2007 Plenary Assembly, Budapest

4. Policy

The ERF – IRF BPC has been active throughout the years to develop a strategy based on providing factual information to key decision makers whilst also being directly involved in issues of interests to the European road community. In its ten years of activity, in fact, the ERF – IRF BPC has frequently intervened in the public debate to offer its view and contribute to the debate over road transport.

In its June 2006 reappraisal of the White Paper on European Transport, the European Commission could legitimately point to a number of achievements since 2001, chief amongst which is drastic cuts in pollutant emissions (-40%) and road fatalities (-17%), and improved working conditions for the millions employed by the transport sector. It must also accept that it has been less than successful in tackling congestion, revitalising Europe's railways or identifying global solutions to help fund the Trans-European Networks.

Enlargement has given the EU a continental dimension and created more transport corridors but at the same time stretched the ability of the Community's financial resources to offer basic accessibility to citizens living in central and eastern Europe.

On the supply side, consolidation is taking place at European level in all transport modes, setting the conditions for increased European competition as motorway operators and haulage firms vie for new markets. Increased investment in research and innovation in areas such as engine technology, intelligent transport systems and infrastructure management are transforming the transport sector into a high-technology industry.

One almost unstoppable trend however is the lasting decline in the capacity of the rail freight industry to service the needs of growing cross-border trade. A report commissioned by the Community of European Railways – hardly the most vocal pro-road advocate – puts the combined losses for the industry at a staggering EUR 800 million a year. In major markets, losses of the freight arm of incumbent rail operators routinely represent 25% of turnover. As volumes go on declining, rail freight operators will face higher overheads, with newcomers unwilling to invest in these markets.

The first casualty of these new trends is a long overdue decision to ditch dogmas hitherto inextricably weaved into the very fabric of our transport policy. In many respects, the situation was comparable to the tale of the Emperor's new clothes with few voices in Brussels daring to suggest that "inter-modality", "modal shift", "marginal cost pricing" and "decoupling" were not bringing Europe anywhere nearer to having a robust, reality-tested, long-term transport policy.

For the road sector, new policy orientations can be expected to translate into measures to foster cooperation between specialists in such key areas as urban transport policy, supply chain management, security energy efficiency or satellite applications in transport. Brussels aficionados are already bracing themselves for a flurry of Green Papers, Public Consultations, Action Plans and White Papers in 2007-2008.

One of the biggest challenges identified by participants to the 2nd European Road Congress (Brussels, 6-8 November 2006) was that intelligent mobility solutions and transport demand management can alleviate congestion to an extent, but new or improved infrastructure is sorely needed. With timetables slipping, inadequate controls on the ground and funds siphoned elsewhere, just eight of the Trans-European Network “priority projects” stand any chance of being completed by 2010. In 2004, the ERF – IRF BPC estimated that 14,000 km of motorways needed to be built within a decade in Central and Eastern Europe to ensure basic levels of accessibility and economic development.

With public financing capacities of the Member States and the Union shrinking, the European Commission needs to overhaul the way it addresses the Trans-European Network and present innovative funding proposals. Current plans to limit community funding to critical cross-border sections are an implicit abandoning of Europe’s grand programme for the construction, modernisation and interconnection of Europe’s major transport infrastructures.

Europe must consider innovative ways to rekindle investment in essential transport infrastructure by mobilising all available sources of financing, notably through the development of hybrid public-private partnerships that combine EU funds with capital market lending. Smart forms of user charging are needed that are at last earmarked to road transport authorities rather than the Treasury.

I. Discussion and Position Papers

Representing the views of a sector as important as the road infrastructure one, it is important that knowledge is transferred so that policy makers can be better informed in their decision making. Discussion and Position papers serve exactly this scope, concentrating important information from a variety of sources into few pages to allow all readers to grasp the topic in discussion.

2007

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| September
June | Discussion Paper – Safety on Motorway Workzones Background Paper and Joint Letter on the Directive on Road Infrastructure Safety Management, published on a dedicated website, www.saferoads.eu |
| April
January | Discussion Paper on Sustainable Roads
Memo to the European Parliament on the Mid-Term Review of the Transport White Paper |

2006

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|----------|---|
| December | 2 nd European Road Congress – findings and Future Perspectives |
| June | Statement on the revision of the Construction Products Directive |
| May | Road infrastructure safety management on the Trans-European Network |
| April | Discussion Paper on Intelligent Roads |
| March | Networks for peace and development – Road transport perspectives in South East Europe |
| January | White Paper revision – ERF speaks out |

<p>2005</p>	<p>November ERF assesses EU Strategic Cohesion Guidelines</p>
<p>2004</p>	<p>December 1st European Road Congress – Summary of key discussion points June Eurovignette: is it a tax, or a toll? May Road Traffic Noise – the ERF perspective March Roads and the Enlargement January The Irish Council Presidency – What Transport Challenges?</p>
<p>2003</p>	<p>October The European Commission's Road Safety Action Programme October Road Restraint Systems – Passive Safety where it matters October Building and Financing a Trans-European Network at the service of Europe's citizens (updated edition) May The ERF's position on achieving a decoupling of transport growth and road deaths May Tunnel Safety Directive – the ERF's position March The ERF's vision of road deaths in 2020: placing the user at the heart of transport policy February The Improvement of Road Signing in Europe January Road Marking Requirements in Europe</p>
<p>2002</p>	<p>December Road Charging – is it fair? December The ERF's position on the rights that should be recognised to users of the European road network March ERF's position on the European Commission's Proposal for a Regulation to Improve the Environmental Performance of the Freight Transport System March ERF's position on the European Commission's White Paper on European Governance March Towards an Efficient Road Transport Network for EU Citizens – Commitment to a European Road Network January ERF's position on the European Commission's Working Paper on Prevention and Restoration of Significant Environmental Damage (Environmental Liability)</p>

2001

October	ERF's position paper on the European Commission's new Common Transport Policy
September	ERF's position paper on Road Transport and Energy Saving
May	ERF position on the European Union's 6th Framework Programme
March	The Socio-economic Benefits of Roads to Society
March	The ERF's position on Road-related exhaust emissions

2000

October	ERF's position paper on Sustainable Investment in Road Maintenance
July	ERF Commitments to the future Common Transport Policy
June	The European Commission's Infrastructure Pricing Effort
June	ERF's position paper on Integrated Transport
March	A different approach to transport data collection at European level

1999

December	ERF's position on the European Commission's "Assessment of Marginal Abatement Costs of Emission Reduction Options of Greenhouse Gases"
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Spotlight on:

European Road Safety Charter

The ERF – IRF BPC was among the founding signatories of the European Road Safety Charter at a ceremony held in Dublin on 6 April 2004. The Charter seeks to inspire its signatories to undertake actions aimed at potentially reducing the number of fatalities on European roads. The Commission's target is to reduce deaths by 50% (25,000 lives) by 2010 and the ERF – IRF BPC has welcomed this initiative and pledged to undertake the following actions as part of its Charter commitments:

- Launching a dedicated quarterly information newsletter (Engineering Safer Roads) for the road community;
- Organising one roundtable per year to bring together industry, government, research and academia;
- The publication of a free yearly brochure to convey practical safety tips to road authorities and motorists.

The European Road Users Charter

The ERF – IRF BPC proposed devising a Road Users Charter based on the principles the European Union is founded upon, namely the universal values of human dignity, freedom, equal rights and solidarity. This Charter sets out to define the rights that should be recognized to all road users of the European highways.

The European Road Users Charter	
	1) Right of access to highway networks
	2) Right to economic and social development
	3) Right to safety
	4) Right to an optimised network
	5) Right to a fair fiscal treatment
	6) Right to information on the state of the network
	7) Right to information on the management of the network
	8) Right to better environmental conditions
	9) Right to network interoperability
	10) Right to fair treatment of all road users
	11) Right to technological progress
	12) Right to a sustainable future

5. Training

The ERF – IRF BPC believes that it is necessary to share best practices at European level so that a harmonisation in the levels of safety of the European road infrastructure can be reached. In order to do so, it has set up a series of training workshops for the benefit of road professionals in Central and Eastern European Countries with the collaboration and support of the Directorate General for Enlargement of the European Commission (TAIEX Unit).

The guiding principles behind the workshops is to offer a comprehensive overview of the safety contribution of better designed, built and operated road networks through interactive presentations delivered by some of Europe's best safety professionals.

Furthermore since the introduction of mandatory auditing requirements by certificate-holding professionals in the future European Commission Directive on "Road Infrastructure Safety Management" (articles 3.2, 4.2, 5.2 and 6.2) is widely expected to generate a surge in demand for training courses, the ERF – IRF BPC will also deliver a European Road Safety Auditing training course to provide participants with a basic understanding of traffic safety parameters enabling them to conduct preventive assessments on new and existing roads and recommend appropriate measures based on sound safety principles.

Workshops in 2007

Istanbul (Turkey)
 Vilnius (Lithuania)
 Budapest (Hungary)
 Bucharest (Romania)
 Skopje (former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia)

Bucharest Workshop

2006

Ankara (Turkey)
 Warsaw (Poland)

2005

Budapest (Hungary)
 Belgrade (Serbia)
 Cacak (Serbia)
 Cairo (Egypt)

Cacak Workshop

6. Research

The IRF's recent decision to launch a Research Council as a global platform of skills committed to improving the sustainability and efficiency of the road sector comes in the wake of almost a decade of direct involvement by the Federation in Europe's road research agenda.

As the world's largest purveyor of research funds, the European Union has long recognised that it needs more and better coordinated research in order to address societal issues (such as societal ageing or climate change) and for its private sector to remain competitive.

European framework programme have practical implications for IRF Members not only as a gateway to community funding, but also because European-funded R&D is often the antechamber of future regulations and standards. As a case in point, ERF – IRF BPC's influential research into Black Spot Management in 2001 was largely instrumental in gathering support for a harmonised approach to preventive infrastructure management which eventually translated into a proposal for a European directive.

Working alongside partners within broad research consortiums has also enabled ERF – IRF BPC to extend its knowledge in areas of practical interest to its Members (such as safety barrier standards or Intelligent Transport Systems, ITS) and become a credible interlocutor for the European institutions. The outcome of these projects has regularly been presented to the road community under the form of workshops and free publications.

This is not to say that the Federation's involvement in co-funded research should be taken for granted or that no challenges remain. An irresistible tendency has been to grab what opportunities presented themselves, without establishing a long term vision of the road community's strategic research needs. IRF research has tended to concentrate in the fields of safety and smart mobility, but many other areas are equally worthy of investigation.

It is partly this lack of governance that the IRF Research Council intends to remedy through more established structures which will help guide our research priorities, lobby for them more effectively and ensure the results will be brought to the attention of those organisations which most need them.

ERF – IRF BPC Research

ERTRAC (ongoing): ERF – IRF BPC is a Steering Committee Member of the European Road Transport Research Advisory Council, a research platform established to develop a shared vision, and ensure coordinated application of research resources to meet the continuing challenges of road transport and European competitiveness.

RANKERS (ongoing): Europe's most comprehensive research initiative to date on road safety engineering, RANKERS will develop a road safety evaluation index and a catalogue of remedial measures ranked according to their efficiency (www.rankers-project.com).

GIROADS (ongoing): a research initiative commissioned by the European GNSS Supervisory Authority to aggregate the road community's proposals facilitating the technical and commercial introduction of Europe's satellite navigation programme to the road sector (www.intelligentroads.org).

EUROAUDITS (2007): developing a harmonised syllabus for road safety auditor training.

OPTIPARK (2005-2007): preparing the market introduction of highly innovative parking services by assessing the feasibility of their trans-European deployment through market validation pilots in six European cities (www.optipark.eu).

ADvantis (2004-2006): as Europe's satellite programme becomes reality, the potential social, economic, technological and environmental benefits of satellite navigation technology to the transport sector are becoming increasingly clear.

RISER (2003-2006): 14,000 European motorists die every year simply by crashing into unprotected roadside objects. How can these accidents be avoided and their consequences mitigated? The RISER project contributed to delivering answers to this key question.

ROBUST (2003-2006): in infrastructural passive safety, road restraint systems are perhaps the single most important roadside element. What can be done to improve their performance at the design and testing stage?

Safeway (2001-2004): an innovative project to develop road barriers with both high-containment and injury-mitigating features built in.

Guidelines to Black Spot Management (2001-2003): A two year research effort on road infrastructure safety coordinated by ERF – IRF BPC which has delivered a comprehensive assessment now available to all road practitioners.

eParking: (2001-2003): can advanced parking management technologies contribute to reducing urban congestion issues?

Tecapsy (2001-2002): this award winning project has altered urban planners' perception of car-sharing.

Spotlight on....GIROADS

In a matter of years, the integrity, continuity, accuracy and availability provided by the GALILEO satellite system will open the doors to new ways of conceiving road transport while at the same time offering new services to a wide range of stakeholders.

GIROADS (**G**NSS **I**ntroduction in the **R**OAD **S**ector) seeks to achieve a shared understanding of the relevance of Europe's satellite navigation programme to the everyday needs of the road transport sector, as a first but decisive step in its ultimate acceptance by the road users themselves. Led by the ERF – IRF BPC, the GIROADS consortium involves some of the most representative actors of the road and GNSS communities.

Spotlight on....RISER

Injuries and fatalities resulting from single-vehicle collisions account for as much as one third of annual European road traffic casualties. This represents 14,000 lives lost each year, a significant proportion of which could be saved through better roadside infrastructure design and management.

The foundation of the RISER work programme was that improved data collection (based on real world crash information) combined with the establishment of guidelines for highway safety professionals (founded on European best practices) can reduce the total number of collisions as well as minimize the severity of those collisions that do occur. By providing a comprehensive input on the do's and don'ts of roadside design and maintenance, RISER has greatly contributed to the goal of aligning the practices of individual Member States.

7. Communication

A clear and concise communication strategy represents one of the most important features of any successful venture, regardless of the sector or the topic in discussion. The right message can deliver a positive image in the eyes of the general public, just as much as a wrong or badly phrased/timed one often seals the doom of certain products/enterprises.

During the ten years of its activity the ERF – IRF BPC has developed a score of communications tools to aid in transmitting its key message that road infrastructure which is safe, green, sustainable and cheap is one of the principal purveyors of the socio-economic well-being of European citizens.

Regular newsletters, press releases, Discussion and Position Papers, its yearly European Road Statistics (www.irfnet.eu/en/2007-statistics) as well as other less regular publications (such as, for instance, the Socio-Economic Benefits of Roads in Europe) all feature in the ERF – IRF BPC’s strategy to further reinforce the key role of well designed, built and maintained roads.

In addition the Federation can pride itself with having a website (www.irfnet.eu) receiving around 100,000 visits every month and containing a wealth of information on all topics of ERF interest as well as acting as an invaluable virtual meeting point for its members through its Members’ Area.

I. Press Releases

Press releases are a fast way to inform a large audience of developments in specific fields. The ERF– IRF BPC issues press releases on a variety of road-related topics, ranging from safety, to construction and Intelligent Roads. Over a sample period of 12 months (June 2006 to June 2007) the Federation issue 18 press releases, averaging 1.5 per month.

Below is an indicative list of press releases for the years 2006 and 2007.

2007

- September EGNOS and GALILEO at the service of urban mobility
- July European Road Statistics 2007
- July Road Safety arrives in Hungary
- July An Open Letter in Support of Higher Safety Levels on Europe’s Roads
- June New Dawn on Road Research
- June A sad day for Road Safety in Europe
- May IRF-EU workshop arrives in Hungary
- April Galileo applications in the road sector
- April Second OPTIPARK Workshop held at PARKEX 2007
- April Better roads good for the environment
- April “Life comes first!”, the Romanian road safety challenge
- March OPTIPARK – Cities continue validation
- February Safety seminars reach Romania
- February Local challenges, regional answers
- January Safety seminars moving around Europe
- January Reserve my place!

2006

- November Working together for a better future
- November Mobility: a competitive advantage for Europe
- October “A victory for Europe’s road users”
- August Leaders to debate the future orientation of European Transport Policy
- July Keep Europe Moving
- July Your Comprehensive Guide to Transport Data
- May Calling for safer road engineering
- May “Better roads, better world” – WEB agrees restructuring and launches a new IRF
- May Where is the Mid-term review of the EU Transport White Paper?
- May Safer road infrastructure saves lives
- March Safety first – Poland’s new approach to road management
- March Roads are major purveyors of GDP, says new ERF publication

II. Speeches & Presentations

The ERF – IRF BPC has often been asked to “bridge the gap” with regards to knowledge in the road transport sector at important events and conferences due to its considerable reputation as a knowledge-based Federation and the availability of its speakers.

Below we offer an indicative list of the most recent interventions of ERF – IRF BPC appointed speakers in Brussels and beyond.

Opening speech - 2nd European Road Congress

(Mr. Jacques Barrot, European Commission Vice-President and Commissioner in charge of Transport, 6 November 2006)

Opening keynote address - 2nd European Road Congress

(Dr. Aniceto Zaragoza, ERF – IRF BPC President, 6 November 2006)

“Honorable President of the House of Representatives, Mr. Vice-President, Dear colleagues and friends,

On behalf of the European Union Road Federation, now a proud component of the International Road Federation, it is a pleasure to be with you this afternoon for the opening session of the 2nd European Road Congress, held in association with Mobility for Prosperity in Europe.

It has been two years since our first Congress saw hundreds of policy-makers and stakeholders converge to Lisbon in an unprecedented consensus-building exercise covering a wide range of crucial transport themes.

I cannot help but recall the wave of cautious optimism that prevailed at the time: the extension of the Union's borders eastwards coupled with the renewal of the European institutions offered the road community a chance to wipe the slate clean and explore new policy options. Naturally, much remains to be done to make Europe's road network interoperable, safe and sustainable, but the inflection given to European transport policy since 2004 constitutes a solid foundation to base our work on.

Honorable President of the House of Representatives, Mr. Vice-President, we feel privileged to have you with us. As you know, the European Union Road Federation, has always strived to set the conditions for a transparent and informed transport policy debate.

It is with this in mind that I now pass the floor to Mr. Herman De Croo President of the Belgian House of Representatives.

Developing the TENs: the point of view of the Road Sector

Robert Schuman Foundation Roundtable

(Dr. Aniceto Zaragoza, ERF – IRF BPC President, 24 May 2005)

Closing Keynote Address - 1st European Road Congress

(Dr. Aniceto Zaragoza, ERF – IRF BPC President, 26 November 2004)

III. Articles

2007

- "The Thought Process" – Thinking Highways, Volume 2 Issue 3
- "European impasse over safety" – Safety & Security for Road Infrastructure, August/September
- "Progress on EU performance standards" – Safety & Security for Road Infrastructure, August/September
- "Sixth edition of European Road Statistics" – World Highways, September
- "Hungary's road safety record in spotlight" – World Highways, September
- "Europa evita el rechazo de la Directiva sobre Seguridad en Infraestructuras Viarias" – Carreteras, July/August
- "Il notiziario ERF – IRF BPC", Strade & Autostrade, July/August
- "Back to drawing board for safer road infrastructure directive" – Europolitics, July
- "Federations and NGOs mobilise for safer road infrastructure" – Europolitics, July
- "The Road Ahead" – Traffic Technology International, June/July

- "Europa no considera prioritaria la mejora de las carreteras en su politica de seguridad vial" – Carreteras, May/June
- "La ERF apuesta por carreteras más sostenibles" – Carreteras, May/June
- "Reuniones estatutarias, en junio" – Carreteras, May/June
- "Green for Go" – Thinking Highways, Volume 2 Issue 2
- "Galileo rilanciato" – Le Strade, June
- "Keep Europe Moving" – World Highways, June
- "A Road for the Future" – Thinking Highways, Volume 2 Issue 1
- "Roads good for the environment, says study" – Euractiv, April
- "Ranking for European road safety" – Safety and Security for Road Infrastructure, February
- "Political will needed or private financing" – World Highways, January/February
- "La AEC participa en un seminario de carreteras en Macedonia" – Carreteras, January/February
- "Come Galileo rivoluzionerà i trasporti stradali" – Le Strade, January/February

2006

- "La sicurezza delle infrastrutture stradali nel mirino della Commissione" – Le Strade, November
- "La Carretera, como modo de transporte dominante, debe combinar eficacia y sostenibilidad" – Carreteras, November/December
- "Road design can improve blackspot safety" – Safety & Security for Road Infrastructure, August/September
- "European Road Statistics: 2006" – Transportation Research Board, August
- "Europe's confusing highways can make for a difficult trip" – Mail & Guardian online, August
- "Road Transport Big contributor to European GDP" – Transport News Network, August
- "Sécuriser le réseau routier européen: l'heure des choix" – Revue Generale des Routes, July/August
- "Call for coordinated approach to European safety" – World Highways, July/August
- "Insurance Quotes" – Traffic Technology International, June/July
- "intelligent Roads" – Traffic Technology International, April/May
- "Road lobby calls for more investment ahead of EU transport policy review" – Euractiv, March
- "Great Enabler" – Traffic Technology International, February/March
- "Survey points to declining road investment" – World Highways, January/February
- "EU transport policy: a revision eagerly awaited" – World Highways, January/February
- "Reality has caught up with ideology" – World highways, January/February
- "Sky's the Limit" – Traffic Technology International, January

2005

- "In a Nutshell" – Traffic Technology International, October/November
- "Infrastructure design and management lie at the heart of road safety" – European Information Services, April
- "A partnership for road safety" – World Highways, April
- "Safe Road Engineering: action call" – World Highways, April
- "EU green light for truck tolls" – Eupolitix, April
- "Shunning Polish Roads" – European Voice, April
- "Crucial questions on EU transport needs" – Financial Times, February
- "EU enlargement offers unique opportunity" – World Highways, January/February
- "Making Europe more mobile" – World Highways, January/February

2004

- "A Lisbona il primo Congresso europeo sulle strade" – Le Strade, December
- "Ha llegado la hora de que Europa tenga su propio encuentro viario" – Carreteras, November/December
- "Transport profesionales gather at 1st European Road Congreso" – World Highways, November/December
- "Una Red Transeuropea al servicio del contribuyente" – Carreteras, September/October
- "Placing the user at the heart of transport policy" – Transport Care, September/October
- "Reach for the sky" – Traffic Technology International, August/September
- "La Asamblea de la ERF se reúne en Moscú con el 1º Congreso Europeo de Carreteras de fondo" – Carreteras, July/August
- "Europe's road challenges under microscope" – World Highways, July/August
- "les routes et l'élargissement de l'Europe: placer l'utilisateur au Cœur de la politique de transport" – Europe de la Route, April

- "Roads and the enlargement: placing the user at the heart of transport policy" – Transport, April
- "What we are actually witnessing is a repeat of the same old tired policies which have markedly failed in the EU" – EU Transport Report, April
- "Question-marks over growth initiative" – E!Sharp, April
- "El transporte por carretera crecerá un 4% anual, según la Federación Europea de Carreteras" – Carreteras, March/April
- "La AEC y la ERF colaboran en el Proyecto Advantis" – Carreteras, March/April
- "Transport and the Enlargement: Time to decide" – European Transport Forum, February
- "La ERF analiza los nuevos proyectos europeos de transporte" – Carreteras, January/February
- "Action plan for Europe" – World Highways, January/February

2003

- "A trans-European network (TEN) at the service of Europe's citizens" – European Roads Review, Special Issue December
- "Sicurezza Stradale: l'UE finanzia il progetto transeuropeo RISER" – Le Strade, November
- "Call for new EU-wide road safety group" – European Voice, October
- "New Action Urged to Cut Road Deaths" – The Scotsman, October
- "Who pays and when?" – World Highways, October
- "EC road financing criticised" – World Highways, October
- "Tomorrow's Transport" – The Parliament, September
- "The European Commission cannot avoid the luxury of an open debate with transport stakeholders" – Euro Transport Intelligence, September
- "Eu's road tolls vision called into question" – Environment Daily, August
- "...and then there was three" – World Highways, July/August
- "Programme d'action européen pour la sécurité routière; Quelle place accordée à l'infrastructure?" – Sécurité des Infrastructures, June
- "Europe's space programme" – Traffic Technology International, February/March

2002

- "Le Livre blanc tient-il la route?" – La Quinzaine Européenne, November
- "Infrastructure charging – is it fair?" – World Highways, September
- "The trans-European Transport Network: need for an urgent, in-depth revision" – Carreteras, July/August
- "Eu's Transport Policy: At the turning Point" – World Highways, January/February

2001

- "The EU's challenges towards a new Common Transport Policy" – Carreteras, April

2000

- "Transport data collection at EU level" – Road Transport Statistics (Eurostat Special Feature), May
- "Transport data collection at EU level" – Traffic & Safety Europe, April

1999

- "The EC's Transport Pricing Effort" – Traffic & Safety Europe, December

IV. Newsletters

The ERF – IRF BPC publishes 4 newsletters regularly throughout the year. The Federation began by publishing one newsletter in 1997 and, due to the great appreciation, expanded its activities to the current level.

Policy & Action is the ERF – IRF BPC Members only newsletter containing a score of information on EU policies, activities of the Federation, upcoming events of interest, road infrastructure developments in Europe and much more. P&A is published bi-monthly, usually in conjunction with all the other newsletters.

As part of the commitment to spread the benefits of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), **Intelligent Roads** is published, a newsletter devoted to the ITS community appearing quarterly.

As part of its commitments after signing the European Road Safety Charter, the ERF – IRF BPC decided to create a newsletter devoted entirely to infrastructure safety. **Engineering Safer Roads** was hence born in 2005 to cover all topics dealing with safer roads. The newsletter is published bi-monthly and is available for consultation on the Federations website.

Voice of the European Road is the Federation e-newsletter aimed at divulging information about activities of the ERF – IRF BPC to the wider public. It is sent to a database of over 3,500 Brussels based stakeholders, who can subscribe to this service via the website.

All the newsletters are available for free consultation and download at the Federations website on <http://www.irfnet.eu/en/erf-publications>, with the exception of Policy & Action which is reserved to global IRF Members only. Additionally ERF Members also receive a printed copy of Intelligent Roads, Engineering Safer Roads and Policy & Action.

V. Publications

ERF – IRF BPC publications offer in-depth information about a specific topic, often with the aid of graphics (as in the case of leaflets), for awareness raising purposes. The European Road Statistics, for instance, published annually and available free of charge through the Federation’s website, is a much sought after publication by policy makers and members of the private sector wishing to become more familiar with key data in the road transport sector.

ERF – IRF BPC publications are normally free, however, in certain cases, a fee is applicable.

2007

- November The Socio-economic benefits of roads in Europe
- October Guidelines to funds supporting Road Research
- October ERF – IRF BPC 10 Year Activity Special
- September Euroaudits brochure
- June European Road Statistics 2007
- June GIROADS brochure

European Road Statistics 2007

2006

- June European Road Statistics 2006
- March The Socio-economic Benefits of Roads in Europe

2005

- October Better road infrastructure – Saving your life
- June European Road Statistics 2005
- June The European Road Users’ Charter
- February The ERF Fact Sheets 2005
- January Guidelines to EU Funds Supporting Road Development

Better road infrastructure – Saving your life

2004

- December 1st European Road Congress Proceedings
- June European Road Statistics 2004
- April Putting you in the driving seat for safer roads

2003

- June European Road Statistics 2003
- February The ERF Infrastructure charging Manifesto
- February The European Road Safety Manifesto
- January Guidelines to Black Spot Management

2002

- December The European Road User Charter
- September Safe driving in Road Tunnels Leaflet
- April European Road Statistics 2002

Safe driving in Road Tunnels

2001

May
March
European Road Statistics 2001
The Socio-economic benefits of roads to Society

2000

November
Sustainable Investment in Road Maintenance

1999

September
Manifesto on European Roads

VI. Website

A website is like an open door allowing every user to access your entire archive in search of a particular document. As such, it needs constant supervision to ensure all the correct material is timely uploaded in the correct sections and pages as well as an occasional “face lift” to improve its looks and functionality. The ERF – IRF BPC’s website, with its over 100,000 monthly visits, surely represents a fitting example of an online “archive” at the disposal of the user, who can, in a matter of a few clicks, reach a score of information on a variety of topics.

When the European Union Road Federation became the Brussels Programme Centre of the International Road Federation, the website **www.erf.be**, which had been the Federation’s website since 1999, was also available through the new address **www.irfnet.eu**, as to reflect the new identity of ERF – IRF BPC.

ERF – IRF BPC website, 1999 to 2007

ERF – IRF BPC website, 2007

8. Events

2007

December	Safe Road Engineering Workshop, Istanbul (Turkey)
October	Safe Road Engineering Workshop, Vilnius (Lithuania)
June	Safe Road Engineering Workshop, Budapest (Hungary)
June	RANKERS Workshop, Budapest (Hungary)
April	OPTIPARK Workshop, Birmingham (United Kingdom)
March	Safe Road Engineering Workshop, Bucharest (Romania)
January	The Safety Benefits of Harmonised Road Signs and Markings, Brussels (Belgium)
January	Safe Road Engineering Workshop, Skopje (former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia)

2006

December	OPTIPARK Workshop, Brussels (Belgium)
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OPTIPARK Workshop

November	2 nd European Road Congress, Brussels (Belgium)
October	A Directive on Road Infrastructure Safety Management, Brussels (Belgium)
September	Engineering Safer Roads Workshop, Ankara (Turkey)
May	Safer Road Infrastructure Saves Lives with EAPA and EUROBITUME, Brussels (Belgium)
May	Passive Safety that Matters (ROBUST final Workshop), Brussels (Belgium)
March	Engineering Safer Roads Workshop, Warsaw (Poland)
February	Innovative approaches in safe road management, Brussels (Belgium)
January	1 st Roundtable on Intelligent Roads, Brussels (Belgium)

2005

November RISER Workshop, Brussels (Belgium)

RISER Workshop

November Engineering Safer Roads Workshop, Budapest (Hungary)

November Engineering Safer Roads Workshop, Belgrade (Serbia)

October Preventive hazard identification, Brussels (Belgium)

June Engineering Safer Roads Workshop, Cacak (Serbia)

March Motorcyclist safety: how can better road engineering help, Brussels (Belgium)

February Engineering Safer Roads Workshop, Cairo (Egypt)

2004

November 1st European Road Congress, Lisbon (Portugal)

October Investing in Road Infrastructure Safety, Cairo (Egypt)

June EU-Russia road seminars, Moscow (Russia)

April Road equipment standardisation – state of play and future perspectives, Brussels (Belgium)

April The Infrastructure Safety Roundtable (in association with World Health Day 2004), Brussels (Belgium)

2002

October Guidelines to Black Spot Management Workshop, Brussels (Belgium)

9. European Road Congress

1st European Road Congress

Lisbon was the host city, between 24-26 November 2004, of the 1st European Road Congress, an event organised by the ERF – IRF BPC to bring together policy makers, industry representatives and members of civil society to share their views on the present and future of road transport.

The three-day event saw the participation of a plethora of speakers and delegates seeking to gather information and to debate over the role of roads in the European Union, with notable interventions from the Portuguese Minister of Public Works, Transport and Communication as well as the President of the Portuguese Road Centre.

1st European Road Congress panel

Delegates discuss during a break

Sponsors of the 1st European Road Congress

2nd European Road Congress

The 2nd European Road Congress was held in Brussels on 6-8 November 2006, drawing hundreds of participants representing all sectors of society and 20 European Member States, making it one of the most significant transport gatherings in 2006.

Opened by European Commission Vice-President Jacques Barrot and Head of the Belgian House of Representatives Herman De Croo, the Congress touched a variety of topics at the heart of the European road transport debate. Topics covered during the thematic sessions included the Mid-Term review of the Transport White Paper, Intelligent Road Transport, Financing the Road Infrastructure, Road Safety, and congestion and the Environment.

At the 2nd European Road Congress policymakers and representatives of civil society concurred in affirming that fostering a realistic and forward-looking road transport policy will have a cascading effect on all sectors of society. All stakeholders attending singled out the presence of an efficient transport infrastructure as being one of the key factors in order to achieve economic development.

Delegates also called for a new drive in the road transport sector, to learn from the lessons of the past and start building together a "New European Transport Policy", whilst also acknowledging the fact that more still needs to be done, especially to influence the negative public perception surrounding road transport which has successfully transformed itself from the perceived "black sheep" to an innovative and sustainable transport mode.

European Commission Vice-President Jacques Barrot

2nd European Road Congress Delegates

Sponsors of the 2nd European Road Congress

EUROPEAN UNION ROAD FEDERATION (ERF)

INTERNATIONAL ROAD FEDERATION (IRF)
Brussels Programme Centre

Avenue Louise 113 - B-1050 Brussels (BELGIUM)

Tel: + (32) 2 644 58 77 Fax: + (32) 2 647 59 34

E-mail: info@irfnet.eu - <http://www.irfnet.eu>